

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1. Heatmap of the SHAP scores from the 380 relevant KDTs predicted (Y - axis) by the model over the 277 circuits related to a SARS-CoV-2 hallmark. The color indicates the SHAP score. Higher SHAP scores depict a higher influence over a specific circuit.

Supplementary Figure 2. Enrichment analysis of the 380 predicted KDTs from functional databases. From left to right, Gene Ontology terms (MF and BP), Human Pathways and Virus related processes.

Supplementary Figure 3. Heatmap of the SHAP scores from the relevant KDTs predicted (Y - axis) by the model summarized by the SARS-CoV-2 infection hallmarks (X - axis). The color indicates the percentage of circuits belonging to a hallmark (X-axis) where the KDT was predicted as relevant. **A)** Depicts KDTs with a spotty influence over the circuits tagged with the hallmarks. **B)** Shows KDTs with a very sustained low (blue) or high (yellow) relevance across the hallmark.

Supplementary Figure 4. Heatmap plot of the normalized (-1,1) SHAP scores from the 109 predictive KDTs (X-axis) over the 209 stable circuits (Y-axis) of the RP Map. The sign indicates the direction of the KDT influence over each specific circuit and the score value depicts how strong is the influence of a specific KDT for predicting the activity of a specific circuit. The top color bar represents the most frequent drug effects of the drugs targeting that specific KDT.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1. Table with DrugBank 5.1.4 database filtered by approved human drugs with known pharmacological action and known protein targets.

Supplementary Table 2. Table with SHAP score of all KDT (columns) over all COVID-19 mechanistic map circuits (rows).

Supplementary Table 3. Table of drugs with relevant KDTs and their influence over the SARS-CoV-2 infection hallmarks hallmarks in terms through the circuits.

Supplementary Table 4. Table of number of genes, and genes in KEGG signaling pathways contained in HiPathia R package sharing an increasing number of RP-HPO terms.

Supplementary Table 5. Table of RP mechanistic map circuits with their code, name (Pathway: effector node), their hallmark/s module/s and the UniprotKB and Gene Ontology functions tagging them.

Supplementary Table 6. Table with DrugBank 5.1.8 database filtered by approved human drugs with known pharmacological action and known protein targets.

Supplementary Table 7. Table of signed SHAP score of all KDT (columns) over all RP mechanistic map circuits (rows).

Supplementary Table 8. Table with selection of predictive KDT (columns) over all RP mechanistic map circuits (rows) in Boolean format (1= selected; 0 = not selected).

Supplementary Table 9. Table with machine learning model performance results (stability and R^2 metrics) over both the whole RP mechanistic map and the per specific circuit models.

Supplementary Table 10. Table with relevant predictive KDTs and their cluster obtained by hierarchical clustering of their SHAP scores (sheet 1). Cluster 1 Panther functional over-representation analysis of GO molecular function and GO biological process (sheet 2). Cluster 2 Panther functional over-representation analysis of GO molecular function and GO biological process (sheet 3). Cluster 3 Panther functional over-representation analysis of GO molecular function and GO biological process (sheet 4).

Supplementary Table 11. Experimental validation data normalized to the values of control mice (100%).

Supplementary Table 12. Table of relevant predictive KDTs with their corresponding drug and pharmacological actions.

Supplementary Table 13. Over-represented categories, with an FDR-adjusted p.value < 0.5 , from the different ATC levels tagging drugs targeting relevant predictive KDTs